

Bring Your Own Portal (BYOP)
HazMapper: An NSF NHERI DesignSafe Cyberinfrastructure Geospatial and Visualization Web Portal

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<https://hazmapper.tacc.utexas.edu/>

Abstract—As part of the cyberinfrastructure that supports NSF NHERI [DesignSafe Cyberinfrastructure](#), [NSF award #2022469](#) web portal, HazMapper is an open-source, geospatial visualization web portal for disaster scientists, researchers, and disaster-impacted individuals to assess natural hazard events' effects. HazMapper's principal scientific goal is to promptly serve the collection of high-quality disaster-related datasets from advanced reconnaissance instrumentation stored in DesignSafe's web portal to visualize and collaborate on natural hazard engineering projects. The portal simplifies access to diverse geospatial data formats, removing the need for specialized software and making published DesignSafe datasets easier to explore. Modeling and simulation are critical to the natural hazard community's goal to understand, simulate, and predict the performance of built, natural, and social systems during and after natural hazard events. The HazMapper web portal handles robust amounts of high-quality geospatial data (such as imagery, point clouds, and vector data) to facilitate critical and time-sensitive disaster mobilizations and enables new research discoveries that protect human life and mitigate damages from natural disasters.

